

ISic3501

I.Sicily inscription 3501

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

stone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336194

1. [— — — — —]
2. [— — —]NIKA
3. [— — —]σα vac.
4. [— — — —]
- 5.
6. [— ὑποκριτῆς ἐ]νίκα
7. [ὁ δεῖνα Σω]σᾶ
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645369

PHI 336194

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1331.7

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 68-69 no.64 fig.146

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